

Child Protection in the Age of Digital Society : A Call for Social Responsibility

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Abstract:- As the family evolves, the children also develop certain habits which become part of their life from the young age. The current family setting is more into implementation of digital technology and it's been misguided by the children due to lack of checking on the gadgets they're using while they study or work. The responsibility as a family is very less as kids become smarter and cunning. The social responsibility in the digital age is very less as children are falling into big traps due to the advancement of technology. Technology can negatively affect children's developing social skills, relationships, health, and overall ability to focus in developing their social skills. This can lead to more being socially awkward, withdrawn, shy, or intimidated by social situations. The children opening more with the outside world is been seen as rise of problem. As family couldn't be role models for them to open fully and show their emotions. The outside world is getting more influenced in the children world of connection. So as a social worker isn't our responsibility to have a one-to-one conversation with our young minds to have a close relationship. Technology is having more control over the human emotions more than the family members and its role of protecting the child is lost somewhere. So as a society it's our social action for the protection of child right from the unwanted digital interactions to personal relationship with the closed network of people. So, who is having more responsibility does the family or the digital world.

Keywords:- Children , Protection, Digital Society , Social Responsibility.

I. INTRODUCTION

The child protection is one of the most prominent topic prevailing in the current scenario and the children are been misguided by the modern technology and its impact on the family members are very high. A child growth means its physical and psychological change process to maturing physical function. The family in the digital era is not much concerned about the health and its concern for the child. New tech cannot be regarded solely as good or hazardous (Syafiuddin et al., 2021). At the one hand, having more access to information, learning digital workplace skills, and having a forum for discussion might be extremely beneficial for the most underprivileged kids. Children have the same human rights as

adults. Regrettably, conversations over children's rights are rarely as heated as those about adult rights or women's rights. There aren't many parties that discuss and take meaningful steps to preserve children's rights. Children are a mirror of the future, as well as assets of family, religion, nation, and state. The purpose of this study is to describe and analyse the meaning of child support in the context of child protection in Indonesia based on the child's best interests. A philosophical and statutory approach was used in this normative legal research. Dias Patricia ET.al (2016) conducted a study among 10 families in various families of international among 6-7year children influenced by technology, how the parents of young children act as the "GATEKEEPER". The analysis or study shows the social design and its impacts on individual life, the study focused mostly on teenagers and the parental style of meditation of technology among teenagers their freedom of choice and their *fundamental right to protection and privacy*. More must be done to optimise, provide for, secure, safe, and participate in young children's technology use. The study conducted by Namita Nagpal, and Suresh Dutt Tripathi(2019)in Delhi NCR Among media and communication academics, there is broad agreement that a significant shift is taking place in young people's media and communication habits. The family's communication culture is in disarray, as are the people. For instance, on the other hand, new digital media has gradually assimilated into urban life. Indian cities and small villages, regulating social relations, on the other, social media that emerged swiftly as a spinoff of new digital media become a significant global source of connectedness for individuals. India due to its vast user base has a unique spot on the social networking sites map. one of its youthful users. teens' use of social networking sites, as well as college-going students, has significantly risen with widespread .

(Sharma, 2013) A family is a fundamental unit of research in many medical and social science areas. Family definitions have changed from nation to country and even within countries. Because of this, along with the changing realities of nowadays, there is a perceived need for redefining the family and the typical family structure types, to study the family as a factor in health and other factors of interest. A "family" redefinition has been proposed, and several subtleties of the word are also examined in length. A strategy for classifying different sorts of families has also been proposed. A few special case scenarios have been thought of, and their categorization under the new approach is explained to further define the categorization

method. A child protection plan applies to over 50,000 children and young people in UK. It is generally known that child abuse is harmful to many areas of child health in the short, medium, and long term. The goal of this study was to expand on current knowledge in order to better understand the role of health in child protection conferences. It attempted to identify the health needs of vulnerable children and young people subject to child protection plans, how health needs are considered at child protection conferences, and which professions advocate for children's and young people's health through the child protection process. (1909_Health_needs_of_vulnerable_children_and_young.Pdf, n.d.)

II. CONCEPTUAL ANALYSIS

The notion of technology has both good and harmful familial consequences. As the home evolves from joint to nuclear, so does technology. As the family develops in the digital era, it creates a new field of discovery for the previous generation to connect and communicate in new ways. The negative repercussions of new technology include a loss in relatives and friends' health and the use of contemporary technology creating a gap among family members, with less activity and interaction and less decision-making in the home setting.

Recognizing the importance of increasing family quality and welfare, the government works hard and has high hopes for the PKH program's success. Right now, PKH is still growing, both in terms of coverage of KPM and coverage of assistance. The Family Development Session (FDS) intervention, also known as the Family Capacity Building Meeting (P2K2), is one example of how programme material is still being developed. (Istiani & Mansyur, 2022)

The North Western University conducted a study with children and parents and the influence of technology on the family system, the use of media in the new technology, the use of the internet by the children in the house and the various change in the behaviour and the attitude of the young and adult child at home, as the survey shows when parents are *making dinner or doing chores* and want to keep their child busy, 87% say they are very or somewhat likely to give their child an activity to do or a toy to play with, 79% to give them a book to read or look at, and 77% to let them watch TV. By comparison, 37% of those who have a smartphone or tablet say they are likely to give them one of those devices to use. (key findings).

(Sarah Husisman 2012). The study shows how parents find it difficult to determine when to restrict their adult child from using the technology and monitoring them. The findings of the researcher show there are constant conflicts and fight happening there as the family could not spend quality time together due to which there are always quarrels happening based on new technology brought at home. The other families find it more convincing and stressful the usage of technology at home children are in the favour of using technology at their

convenience ICT influence on diverse family activities is a recurring topic for research as technology advancements advance at an ever-increasing rate. Parents and children are found to employ the ICT tools similarly, excluding activity preference. Parents favour ICT more than youngsters prefer education, creating social networks, etc., whilst adults choose entertainment. Aside from the negative and positive aspects of ICT families.

Although physical sexual activity between children is now largely accepted within the context, the sexual exploitation of children through the use of ICTs has rekindled the social stigma associated with child sexuality. Children and adolescents under the age of 18 account for one-third of all internet users globally.

The children are lose in the digital world so much that they are forgetting the harmful effects and the influence of digital era in the life. The children are becoming victims and addicts to the digital world as its creating meta world for them to enjoy and its creating different psychological imbalance in them . Children and young people may have physical, emotional or mental health problems of their own, including disabilities and special needs or speech and language difficulties, Increasing numbers of our young people have mental health difficulties.

One significant risk concerns children's private lives. Many kids use social media to upload significant personal information and photographs that may possibly remain online for lengthy periods of time. This information may have a negative impact on their life if it is used by educational institutions or possible employers in the future. Profiling information and retaining data on children's Internet activity for commercial purposes presents privacy problems, which most youngsters are not aware of. (Katz, n.d.) Availability to social media, online conversations, and games has created opportunities for inquiry and interaction, but also concerns such as cyberbullying, online grooming, and online sexual assault. Early childhood development experts are concerned about the rising amount of hours youngsters spend gazing at screens. Psychologists advise against using screen time as a reward, i.e. giving children screen time if they perform a duty or activity. (unicef, n.d.). At least 80% of young people have been seen using social media websites like Facebook for communication, thanks to technological innovation and new means of communicating with people anywhere in the globe. Social media and the digital world in general may lead to hazardous online settings, even while they can be useful for interacting with like-minded individuals and other good things. This is because the rules created to protect people online have not yet kept up with how quickly the technology is expanding. Despite the fact that toxic behaviour on social media is becoming more common due to increased usage, the digital world allows academics and social media users to look into brand-new issues or topics that did not exist 50 years before, such as cyberbullying and its effects on young people, in order to address them. (Salafia, 2017)

III. PUBLICATION REVIEW

Table 1 Data Base For The Paper

SrNo	Keywords	No. of reviews	Authors & Year of publication
1.	<i>Child protection</i>	5	(Jaipong et al., n.d.; Katz, n.d.; Syafiuddin, Safa'at, & Djatmika, 2021; Syafiuddin, Safa'at, Djatmika, et al., 2021; unicef, n.d.; Witting, 2019)
2.	<i>Social responsibility</i>	5	(El Ghoul et al., 2016; Ma, 2023; Rehman et al.,(Rossi, 2001), (Wray-Lake & Syvertsen, 2011) (Chiffi et al., 2022)
3.	<i>Digital technologies</i>	13	(UNICEF <i>Children in a Digital World 2017</i> , n.d.), (Leggett & Rossouw, 2014, Vasanth et al.,2021 , (Bashkireva et al., 2022; Krick et al., 2019; Ohlert et al., 2022; Tianchong Wang & Chariya Chiumkanokchai, 2022; Vedeckhina & Borgonovi, 2021), (Ajayi et al., 2022), (Chiffi et al., 2022),(Salafia, 2017)

To build this conceptual paper, several secondary data sources were examined. After that, list was filtered down to the most pertinent ones that may support the conceptual development in this article. 20 secondary data were examined, and one of the main requirements was that they have been released after 2000. The information was gathered from academic journals, websites, web reports, articles, ResearchGate, springler, Shodh Ganga, google books.

IV. DISCUSSION

The role of social responsibility needs to be taken in the ways of the child protection is very less spoken in the Indian context and its more advanced and seen in the international school and houses. The child protection is very much important in the rising use of technology and its role of family members is very high and social action always come from the home and its first place where the child learn its basic. The social responsibility among children should be very high in dealing with the responsibility to which a child should be known. The social responsibility among the family members should be the environment where ethical and cultural values are achieved in a natural way. As basic and essential building blocks of societies, families have a crucial role in social development. They bear the primary responsibility for the education and socialization of children as well as instilling values of citizenship and belonging in the society. social responsibility is been defined as the set values or personal commitment to improves ones community and society. Transitions to middle school put adolescents at risk for a variety of disruptions such as declines in academic competencies and motivation, self-esteem, and mental. If adolescents perceive school climates as more unfriendly and as placing more emphasis on competition and achievement after transitioning to middle or high school, they may also perceive less support for prioritizing concerns for others.(Rossi, 2001) Social responsibility is a value orientation that inspires some civic behaviours and is based on moral ideals of justice and caring in democratic relationships with others. Developmental researchers and youth workers should put more of an emphasis on the development of social responsibility among individuals given its importance for fostering healthier relationships and communities. The emergence of executive function, empathy

and emotion control, and identity during childhood and adolescence are the developmental foundations of people's social duty. Children and adolescents should be encouraged to express their concern for others, model prosocial behaviour, and participate in civic activities as part of their daily life in order to develop their social responsibility.(Wray-Lake & Syvertsen, 2011) as the setting where cultural and ethical values are attained in a natural way. Families have a critical role in the social evolution of societies as the fundamental and indispensable building elements. They are primarily responsible for the upbringing, education, and socialisation of children as well as for teaching civic virtues and a sense of community. Families protect their members from hardship to the greatest extent possible by providing them with both technical and quasi care and support, whether they are young children, elderly people, or those who are unwell(Chiffi et al., 2022)

V. CONCLUSION

The social responsibility should be start from the family and its member because child inspires some civic behaviours and is based on moral ideals of justice and caring in democratic relationships with others. The family in the age of digital society should be more vigilant and be more responsible in handling the technology with the children with SMART (SPECIFIC , MEASURABLE , ACCEPTED , REALISTIC AND TIME BOUND)to the use of the technology by the children for their safety and the responsibility to handle the digital world .the family should more responsible and in handling the technology more the child for the protection of child from digital abuse , mental imbalance due to over usage of digital devices and its behavioural changes.

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